

Figure S1: Experimental setup used to establish combined gradients of irradiance and temperature in the growth chamber. Plants were arranged in a matrix under the RGB LED panel and the infrared heating panel, creating a two-dimensional gradient of light and temperature across the experimental area. Only plants marked with white labels were included in subsequent analyses. Plants positioned directly under the panels were excluded and served as reserve individuals. The photograph shows the plants after 14 days of acclimation to the gradient conditions.

Table S1: Gradient of mobile phases used for the separation of phenolic compounds in leaf extracts of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Mobile phase (A) 5% acetonitrile + formic acid 999:1 (v/v) and (B) 80% acetonitrile + formic acid 999:1 (v/v).

Time [min]	A [%]	B [%]
0	100	0
2	95	5
5	92	8
8	90	10
12	85	15
13.5	85	15
17	65	35
19	20	80
21.5	0	100
24	0	100
24.5	100	0
31	100	0

Table S2: Generalized additive models were used to evaluate relationships between pairs of predictors and response variables related to carbon allocation, nutritional status, and plant growth. For each relationship, three model structures were compared: additive models with separate smooth terms for each predictor ($s(x) + s(y)$), additive models including tensor-product interaction terms to test for non-additive effects ($s(x) + s(y) + ti(x, y)$), and fully bivariate smooth models describing joint response surfaces ($s(x, y)$). Panel **A** shows model comparisons for the relationship between the C/N ratio and $\ln(\text{NSC})$ predicting $\ln(\text{PheCs})$, whereas panel **B** shows model comparisons for the relationship between the C/N ratio and $\ln(\text{PheCs})$ predicting $\ln(\text{DW})$. All models were fitted using the *mgcv* package with REML estimation. The table reports adjusted R^2 (Adj. R^2), effective degrees of freedom (EDF), and p-values for individual smooth terms in additive models, interaction terms (ti), and bivariate smooths. Significance of interaction terms reflects comparisons between additive models with and without tensor-product interactions. Significance codes: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns $p \geq 0.05$.

A

Model	Formula	Adj. R^2	C/N		NSC		Interaction		p_(C/N, NSC)	
			p_value	EDF	p_value	EDF	p_value	EDF	p_value	EDF
C/N \times $\ln(\text{NSC}) \rightarrow \ln(\text{PheCs})$	$s(x) + s(y)$	0.268	*** < 0.001	1.81	ns ≥ 0.05	0	–	–	–	–
	$s(x) + s(y) + ti(x, y)$	0.287	* < 0.05	1	ns ≥ 0.05	1	ns ≥ 0.05	8	–	–
	$s(x, y)$	0.325	–	–	–	–	–	–	*** < 0.001	4.22

B

Model	Formula	Adj. R^2	C/N		PheCs		Interaction		p_(C/N, PheCs)	
			p_value	EDF	p_value	EDF	p_value	EDF	p_value	EDF
C/N \times $\ln(\text{PheCs}) \rightarrow \ln(\text{DW})$	$s(x) + s(y)$	0.386	* < 0.05	2.43	ns ≥ 0.05	1.86	–	–	–	–
	$s(x) + s(y) + ti(x, y)$	0.511	ns ≥ 0.05	2.58	*** < 0.001	1	ns ≥ 0.05	5.96	–	–
	$s(x, y)$	0.594	–	–	–	–	–	–	*** < 0.001	11.04